

Notes

Uranium(IV) Carboxylates. Part II—Tartarate Compounds of Uranium(IV)

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IN continuation of our investigation in the synthesis of uranium(IV) carboxylates^{1,2,3}, we report the isolation of a few more tartarate compounds of uranium(IV) with their probable structures.

Materials and Methods: The chemicals used were either of AnalaR B.D.H. or Fluka qualities.

Preparation of uranium(IV) ditartarate, $U(C_4H_4O_6)_2$: The solution obtained by reduction of uranyl formate in sunlight in presence of a few ml of formic acid was treated with a solution of tartaric acid when a light green precipitate formed. The solution along with the precipitate was further exposed to sunlight for 8-10 hrs when the light green compound settled down. It was filtered, washed with water, and finally with ethanol and dried in vacuum. The uranium content of the compound was estimated as U_3O_8 as reported earlier. The carboxylate content was estimated by acid-alkali titration.

The compound was sparingly soluble in water ($4.31 \times 10^{-3} M$ at 26°), insoluble in organic solvents, but soluble in aqueous solution of tartaric acid or alkali tartarates forming a green solution.

Preparation of complex salts of the ion $[UT_3]^{-2}$: On adding uranium(IV) ditartarate to a hot aqueous solution of tartaric acid, alkali tartarate, sodium potassium tartarate or sodium hydrogen tartarate in the molar ratio 1:1 a deep green solution resulted. The solution was filtered and evaporated at low temperature. A light green mass was obtained. This was washed with alcohol, dried in vacuum and analysed. An

aqueous solution of either $H_2[UT_3]$ or $M_2[UT_3]$ when treated with barium chloride solution yielded a dirty green precipitate. It was filtered, washed with alcohol, dried in vacuum and analysed. The analytical data are given in Table 1.

Uranium(IV) ditartarate goes into solution forming a green solution when it is added to an aqueous solution of alkali tartarate.

Solubility of uranium(IV) ditartarate in the solution of sodium tartarate of various concentration was determined at 26° and the equilibrium constant (K) of the reaction (1) was calculated. The average for K was found to be 4.5×10^3 .

Discussion

The molar conductivity data of the complexes (Table 1) indicate that the complexes are bi-univalent electrolytes. The slightly higher values in a few cases can be explained by the fact that the complexes undergo hydrolysis in aqueous solution, which is evident from the pH drop of the aqueous solutions of the complexes with time.

IR spectra: In the ir spectra of these complexes a strong and broad band is observed in the region 3400 cm^{-1} . These bands arise due to O-H stretching vibrations of water and secondary alcoholic groups. The broadness of the band indicates the presence of intramolecular hydrogen bonding in these complexes. The ir spectra of uranium(IV) ditartarate, UT_2 and its complexes show $\nu_{as}(\text{OCO})$ in the region $1600-1650 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ as compared to 1750 cm^{-1} in d-tartaric acid indicating that both the carboxylate groups are coordinated to uranium(IV) ion.

The symmetric stretching vibrations of (OCO) group for all the compounds are located in the region $1340-1410 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The ir spectra in the region $1000-1200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ show significant differences between uranium(IV) ditartarate, UT_2 and the rest of the complex salts. While there is no band in this region in the case of uranium(IV) ditartarate, there is a group of three sharp

TABLE I
ANALYTICAL AND MOLECULAR CONDUCTIVITY DATA

Compounds	Uranium %		Tartarate %		Molecular conductivity $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$
	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	
UT_2	44.45	44.58	55.78	55.44	—
$H_2UT_3 \cdot H_2O$	33.90	33.81	63.25	63.95	—
$Na_2UT_3 \cdot 4H_2O$	29.75	29.47	37.72	37.00	243.3
$K_2UT_3 \cdot 8H_2O$	26.50	26.32	32.87	32.74	—
$(NH_4)_2UT_3 \cdot H_2O$	32.65	32.33	40.92	40.32	259.0
$(NaK)UT_3 \cdot H_2O$	31.47	31.23	39.61	38.85	259.0
$(NaH)UT_3 \cdot 6.5H_2O$	29.29	29.35	46.74	45.62	281.8
$BaUT_3$	29.33	29.06	35.86	36.14	—

(Ba% : found 16.30, calcd. 16.58)

bands of medium to strong intensity in the complex salts. Tartaric acid shows the OH deformation vibration at 1275 cm^{-1} which disappears in uranium(IV) ditartarate indicating that the OH groups are coordinated to uranium(IV) ion. The $\nu_s(\text{OCO})$ band as reported above in this compound is relatively broader than all other complex salts which further implies that this band arises due to a combination of several superimposed bands.

In complex salts the observed bands in this region appear on both higher as well as lower frequency side of 1275 cm^{-1} band and clearly imply that the OH groups are dissimilar and most probably only one of the OH group is coordinated to uranium(IV) ion. In addition to the above spectral data, the spectra of d-tartaric acid show a peak at 1097 cm^{-1} which arises due to C-O stretching vibration of the secondary alcoholic group (C-OH). In uranium(IV) ditartarate and its complex salts this band shifts to a lower frequency region $1085\text{--}1049\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and appears as a doublet. The splitting indicates that both the (C-OH) groups are dissimilar in these compounds.

It appears from the above discussion that tartarate ion coordinates through two carboxylate groups and a hydroxy group to a uranium(IV) ion and the secondary hydroxy group being coordinated to a neighbouring uranium(IV) ion. The splitting of the (C-OH) stretching band appears due to differences in vibrational energies of the coordinated OH group in the chelate ring and the coordinated OH group with the neighbouring uranium(IV) ion.

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Some Ni(II) Complexes of 4-Thiazolidinone Derivatives

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WE describe in this paper the preparation and characterisation of some Ni(II) complexes with 2-phenyl-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinone derivatives¹, having phenyl, *p*-chlorophenyl and *p*-methoxyphenyl groups in position 3.

Experimental

The three ligands (I) have been prepared by the condensation of proper Schiff bases with thiomalic acid following the procedures described in literature^{1,2,3}.

Where R = phenyl, *p*-chlorophenyl or *p*-methoxyphenyl.

Equimolar quantities of nickel chloride in distilled water and the ligands in rectified spirit were mixed and the pH was adjusted between 6 to 6.5 by means of acetate buffer. The mixture was refluxed for 1 hr. Separated solids were filtered, washed with hot water and then with alcohol. The complexes were dried in vacuum at room temperature. All the complexes were insoluble in water and common organic solvents and were only partially soluble in DMF. Data on elemental analysis, thermal analysis, magnetic moment at room temperature, electronic and ir spectra are stated in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analysis shows the complexes to be 1:2::M:L with two water molecules. Thus the ligands behave as bidentate monobasic groups and with two water molecules give a six-coordinate Ni(II) complex. The low conductivity (about 10 mhos) indicates the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. The T.G.A. residues are in accordance with the suggested composition of the molecules. DTA curves show an endothermic peak between $140\text{--}175^\circ$ which suggests the presence of water; decarboxylation sets in at around 320° in all these complexes.

The values of the experimental magnetic moments of the complexes are found to lie in the range of 3 to 3.2 B.M. suggesting an octahedral stereochemistry⁴. All the complexes show absorption bands at around 360 nm and 420 nm which are also present in the ligands. They further show three more bands which are weak. These bands could be due to the following idealised (O_h symmetry) transitions. The bands at 450 nm ($\epsilon=770$), 530 nm ($\epsilon=300$) and 640 nm ($\epsilon=120$) could be ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(\text{P})$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(\text{F})$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ transitions respectively.

The ir spectra of the complexes show a broad peak around 3500 cm^{-1} confirming the presence of water molecules. A band around 1720 cm^{-1} in all the complexes shows the presence of C=O group. It is not shifted from its position in the ir spectrum of the ligands. Hence we conclude that the C=O group does not enter into complex formation. A very weak band near 750 cm^{-1} could be assigned to rocking vibration of water attached to nickel. The complexes show two sharp bands at $\sim 1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 1400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to the COO^- group. The second bond of ligand to Ni(II)